

**MICROSTRUCTURAL EVOLUTION AND MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF
CRYOMILLED NANOGRAINED NEAR AI-5083 ALLOY FOLLOWING
DEFORMATION PROCESSING**

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Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements for the Degree of
Master of Science in Materials Engineering

New Mexico Institute of Mining and Technology
Socorro, New Mexico
December, 2014

ABSTRACT

Nanocrystalline Al-Mg alloys are being considered for light weight transportation applications because they possess significantly higher strength than the conventional coarse grained alloys. Failure strengths higher than 1000 MPa have been reported for Al-5083 alloy at New Mexico Tech, which are almost double the strength of commercial precipitation strengthened Al-alloys. Unfortunately, the ductility tends to exhibit inverse relationship to strength and therefore there is a need to find ways to increase the ductility while maintaining high strength.

In this work, we utilize a near Al-5083 alloy that was cryomilled for 24 hours in liquid nitrogen environment and consolidated by vacuum hot-pressing. The as-atomized Al-Mg powder was especially fabricated to minimize undesired impurity content to prevent premature fracture from intermetallic particles. It turned out that the final composition was slightly lower in Mn and Mg content and so the alloy is better designated as a near Al-5083 alloy. The as-vacuum hot pressed material had poor ductility because of inadequate prior-particle bonding, and therefore was subjected to deformation processing using low strain-rate extrusion at elevated temperatures. Both the strain-rate and temperature of extrusion were varied in an effort to obtain a good combination of tensile strength and ductility. In addition, the samples were annealed following extrusion in order to reduce residual stresses.

The microstructure of extruded samples were characterized using a combination of electron microscope and X-ray diffraction techniques, and revealed a multi-scale morphology that could be binned into three different sizes of grains: i) those less than 100 nm that were analyzed using the X-ray based Williamson-Hall technique and transmission electron microscopy (TEM), ii) grain sizes in the 100-300 nm regime that were best revealed using TEM and scanning electron microscope (SEM) based electron-backscatter diffraction (EBSD) techniques, and, iii) elongated larger grains with lengths in the range 3 to 7 μm that were observed using EBSD. Room temperature tensile tests with small tensile samples indicated that ultimate strengths in the range 740-760 MPa and elongation to failure better than 2.5%. These data could be produced reproducibly following extrusion at 400 C at an average strain rate of 0.05/sec, and fractography revealed a rough topography with large pull out regions that consisted of typical ductile dimple void growth at the 200-500 nm scale, while in other regions the dimples were very shallow that would suggest failure with little energy loss likely in regions of nanograins less than 100 nm. The combination of strength and ductility in the material are some of the best that have been reported for Al-5083 alloys, and likely a result of the multi-scale microstructure resulting from processing through the cryomilling and extrusion plus annealing procedures.

Keywords: Nanocrystalline Alloys; Al 5083; Cryomilling; Extrusions

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

I would like to thank my academic and research adviser, Dr. Bhaskar Majumdar, for his support and guidance throughout my research. I am also grateful to Dr. David Burleigh and Dr. Nikolai Kalugin for their advice, and for serving on my committee.

I sincerely thank DWA Aluminum Composites (Chatsworth, CA) for providing materials of this research. I would like to thank Dr. Yongho Sohn and Clara Hoffmiester from University of Central Florida for assisting with TEM analysis. I am also thankful to Dr. Aaron Pedigo at NSWC, Crane, Indiana for his assistance with EBSD analysis.

My sincere thanks go to Mr. Gary Chandler and Dr. Virgil Leuth for giving permission to use SEM and X-ray Diffractometer. I also want to thank the graduate students of Materials and Metallurgical Engineering Department at New Mexico Tech, especially Michael Apemah, Oluwaseyi Olamide Ayodeji, Michael McCleod, Mekan Ovezmyradov, Matthew Schmitt, Idil Ayan, & Sohrab Khalifeh for their support all the time.

This work was funded through Army Contractual Agreement W911NF-11-2-0036, monitored through the Army Research Laboratories. I sincerely thank Dr. Kyu Cho, the contract monitor as well as Dr. Anit Giri at ARL. Financial support from the Army Research Laboratory is gratefully acknowledged.

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CHAPTER 1: INTRODUCTION

1.1 Motivation

Nanostructured metallic alloys are of great interest in structural applications due to their superior mechanical properties compared to conventional alloys. A primary variable influencing strength is the grain size, and the well known Hall-Petch (HP) relationship states that strength or hardness increases inversely with the square root of grain size [1-4]. Thus when the grain size is decreased to the nano level, a large increase in strength is observed.

From an application viewpoint, nano Al-alloys are particularly interesting because they offer a combination of high strength and light weight or equivalently high specific strength. While the aerospace industry has capitalized on precipitation strengthened Al-alloys such as Al-2024 to fulfill specific strength requirements, such alloys suffer from poor weldability and corrosion resistance. Land based transportation therefore often turn to Al-Mg alloys (i.e. 5XXX alloys) for meeting property requirements albeit at lower strength. Indeed, the alloy Al 5083 has been used in the construction of military vehicles because of improved weldability, corrosion resistance and ballistic properties [5]. The BAE Systems' Assault Amphibious Vehicle (AAV7A1), deployed frequently by the U.S. Marine Corps has a hull made from Al 5083 alloy. The alloy has adequate combination of ultimate tensile strength (300 MPa [6], for Al-5083-H112), weldability, and corrosion resistance in a marine environment. However, an increase in the strength of the Al 5083 while retaining its weldability and corrosion resistance is desirable, because it would reduce weight and decrease fuel consumption and therefore an overall performance improvement. Lee et al reported a peak flow strength of 847 MPa for an Al-7.5 Mg alloy prepared by powder metallurgy that involved cryomilling followed by hot isostatic pressing (HIP) technique [7]. This may be compared with the flow stress of only 300 MPa for a conventional Al 5083-H112 alloy.

Powder metallurgy (P/M) processed nanocrystalline Al-alloys suffer from poor ductility [8]. Thus, Apemah noted an ultimate compressive strength of 1050 MPa for cryomilled and high strain rate processed Al 5083 alloy, while the ductility was essentially zero [9]. Deformation processing improved the ductility to about 2%, albeit at significant strength reduction. Sequential ABC plane-strain forging was the approach that was adopted for deformation processing, but the repeatability was not adequate. In particular, the friction effect was large because of small thickness-to-length ratio in the plane-strain forgings, and this may have resulted in ductility variation in the tensile samples.

Therefore, in this research on cryomilled Al-Mg alloy, two changes were incorporated. First, the Mg-content has been reduced slightly to minimize the incidence of MgO, MgAl₂, AlCrMg and Al-Mg-Fe second phases that were observed earlier, also discussed

by others [10, 11]. The rationale was that such second phase particles could be responsible for premature crack nucleation, although they have the beneficial effect of inhibiting stress induced grain growth during secondary processing [10]. In addition, Cr and Fe in the alloy were reduced to prevent the formation of brittle intermetallics. Second, an extrusion approach was utilized because it reduced the number of deformation processing steps. Thereby, a better reproducibility was anticipated, and the current results suggest that the approach has been effective.

CHAPTER 2: LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Processing of Nano Crystalline Alloys

A bulk material with nanometer-scale grains can be achieved by a number of techniques. Most of these methods, however, are only capable of producing small volumes for research purposes and are difficult to scale up to large quantities needed for structural applications. In powder metallurgy (P/M) based approaches, nanocrystalline powders can be produced in one of two forms: i) a change of physical state, such as gas condensation or rapid solidification, is utilized to form nanometric particles of the order of 5 -10 nm [4]. In the second approach, the powder particles themselves may be of micron size, but the microstructure of the particles is nanocrystalline, having a grain size in the 10–100 nm range [12]. Such particles can be produced by cryomilling. Cryomilling is a mechanical attrition technique in which powders are milled in a slurry formed with milling balls and a cryogenic liquid such as liquid nitrogen. The powders are subject to repeated impact deformation by the milling media such that dislocation densities become high enough for them to organize into substructures that ultimately lead to the formation of both low and high angle grain boundaries of nanometer dimensions. The particles no longer remain round but subdivide into smaller flattened particles, each containing a nano crystalline microstructure. Ball milling is a stochastic process, and so it is likely that some regions may not be deformed sufficiently and so may contain sizes that are larger than nano crystalline grains. One problem with P/M technique in general is that they exhibit lower ductility. Therefore, other techniques collectively known as severe plastic deformation (SPD) have been developed which operate on ingot metallurgy processed material, and produce nano crystalline grains by repeated plastic deformation mostly at room temperature (RT) or slightly elevated temperatures [13]. Some of these techniques are equal channel angular pressing (ECAP), high pressure torsion (HPT), twist extrusion (TE), and multi-axial forging [13]. There are limitations on the maximum sizes of material that can be produced with these techniques, but they yield better tensile ductility than P/M based material and so remain a favorite for a number of structural applications. As pointed out earlier, nanocrystalline material prepared by cryomilling has the potential to be easily scaled up to large dimensions [14] and in addition the thermal stability of nanocrystalline powders are outstanding [8, 15]. The latter helps to perform deformation processing at elevated temperatures while avoiding excessive growth of nanograins to sizes of tens of micrometers with accompanied large losses in strength.

Extremely high strength of the consolidated materials has been reported for nanocrystalline Al 5083 alloys produced by cryomilling [12]. Non-metallic elements incorporated during cryomilling, particularly nitrogen from the surrounding liquid, impart

excellent thermal stability to Al-containing alloys and help to retain the grain size small after consolidation of the powder at high temperature [14].

2.1.1 Cryomilling

The cryomilling technique was developed at Exxon Research and Engineering [12]. Cryomilling (i.e., ball milling at cryogenic temperatures) is a mechanical attrition technique. The raw material, generally a powder, is milled in a slurry formed with milling balls (typically steel balls of high hardness) and a cryogenic liquid, normally N_2 . The milling attritor is comprised of a rotating impeller contained within a vessel. The vessel is modified to accommodate a continuous flow of liquid nitrogen into the mill, as shown in Figure 1. To maintain a constant milling environment, thermocouple probes are inserted into the milling vessel to monitor the temperature of the mill and the level of liquid nitrogen throughout the milling.

Typically, a stainless-steel vessel, impeller, and milling balls are used, with a ball-to-powder mass ratio of $\sim 30:1$. The impeller is rotated at 180 rpm and milling is carried out over a period of 8 h.

Figure 1: A schematic diagram of a typical cryomilling apparatus. [5]

Being trapped between the balls during collisions, the particles of the powder are repeatedly deformed by compressive and shear stresses. As the starting particles are ductile, initially the particles are plastically deformed and form flakes. When two or more particles are trapped between the balls, they are crushed and cold-welded together to form particles of a larger size with a lamellar structure. This reduces the effect of milling. To prevent excessive welding, a process control agent (PCA) is added to the milling slurry. The PCA is an organic compound, often stearic acid [16-18].

As the dislocation density and the amount of interstitial impurities such as nitrogen from the surrounding liquid increase, the particles become stronger and more brittle. This causes the powder to fracture more readily and leads to a reduction in particle size and a further change in morphology. The milling in a liquid nitrogen environment is beneficial due to the fact that nitrogen containing dispersoids, with dimensions in the nanoscale, are formed, which can increase the strength of the alloy by the pinning of dislocations. More importantly, the major impact of these nitrogen-containing dispersoids particularly for aluminum-containing alloys is that they substantially increase the thermal stability of the microstructure. This is important in retaining a small grain size during consolidation of the cryomilled powder and subsequent secondary processing. Else, a combination of straining, temperature and pressure would lead to rapid grain growth.

The period of cryomilling is also an important variable that influences final grain size. Longer cryomilling time is found to result in smaller grain size. For instance, in Al-7.5Mg alloy, cryomilling for 1 hour yielded nano grain size of about 70 nm whereas cryomilling for 16 hours yielded grain size of about 20nm [12] as shown in Figure 2. Currently, 20-25 nm appears to be a limit on the smallest grain size that could be obtained by the cryomilling technique for Al alloys. This was indeed the size of our powders, as analyzed using both XRD and TEM techniques.

Figure 2: Grain size as function of milling time for cryomilled and ball milled powders [12]

2.1.2 Mechanism of Grain Size Refinement

The grain refinement process during milling is accomplished via the formation of shear bands under localized deformation. These shear bands are typical for deformation mechanisms that occur at high strain rates in contrast to slip mechanism at low and moderate strain rates. Grain refinement during cryomilling is dominated by total lattice microstrain. The widely accepted mechanism of nanostructure formation by milling is the grain subdivision mechanism [12, 16, 19]. Grain refinement by cryomilling is a three-

stage process. Initially, the deformation is localized in shear bands consisting of an array of dislocations with high density. At certain strain level, the dislocations annihilate and recombine to nanometer-scale sub-grains. This sub-grain structure extends throughout the sample during continued milling. At the final stage, the sub-grain boundaries transform to randomly oriented high-angle grain boundaries implying grain rotation. A schematic of the grain refinement process is given in Figure 3 [12].

Figure 3: Schematic representation of grain refinement mechanism during cryomilling [12]

Elongated grains may be present after milling and are often associated with insufficient milling time [8].

2.1.3 Thermal Stability of Cryomilled Al Alloys

The thermal stability of the cryomilled Al alloys is important for consolidation of the powder particles into bulk form without coarsening the microstructure and therefore retaining a good combination of strength and ductility in the nanocrystalline state. Luton *et al.* first applied the cryomilling process to a mixture of aluminum and alumina powders and found that the subsequent material had nanoscale grain sizes and was thermally stable [20]. The thermal stability was attributed to aluminum oxynitride and aluminum oxide particles dispersed at the grain boundaries, reported by Susegg *et al.* [20].

In Al 5083 cryomilled alloy, there are dissolved species of Mg, Mn, Cr, Fe, Si, O, and N and also the second phase particles of Mg_2Si , AlN , Al_2O_3 , and $Cr_2Mg_3Al_{18}$. The tremendous thermal stability of cryomilled nanostructured Al 5083 alloys results from the combined effect of the grain boundary segregation of the atomic species and the Zener pinning of the grain boundaries by nanoscale nitrogen and oxygen rich second phase particles [20-22].

2.1.4 Degassing and Consolidation

As the grain size is in the nano scale, the powder has very high strength. To take advantage of this increased strength in a bulk form, the cryomilled powder must be consolidated. After the cryomilling in the attritor, the powder needs to be handled in an

inert gas to prevent the formation of oxides and hydroxides by reaction with oxygen or moisture in the atmosphere. Thus, prior to consolidation, the powder should be stored in a sealed can as soon as possible after milling. At this point, figure 4 would be helpful to understand the processing [23].

Figure 4: Schematic of processing steps required to generate nanostructured alloy [23]

The PCA used during powder milling is a source of hydrogen, which is very detrimental to the ductility of the end product. Therefore, the powder needs to be hot-vacuum degassed [24]. Stearic acid ($C_{18}H_{36}O_2$), for example, breaks down under the application of heat at about 300 C and most of the hydrogen can be removed. Removal of the hydrogen is aided by longer times, particularly for large cans of powder, and higher temperatures, although excessive grain growth has to be avoided. In situ monitoring of the level of vacuum is generally utilized to confirm that gaseous entrapment is reduced to a minimum level before the degassed cans are sealed in preparation for powder consolidation by vacuum hot pressing (VHP), hot isostatic pressing (HIP), or cold isostatic pressing (CIP) techniques. The typical grain size of as-cryomilled Al-5083 powders is about 25 nm and they grow to about 50 nm in the as-VHP condition.

In HIPing technique, the canned powder is heated to $\sim 400^\circ\text{C}$ and simultaneously subjected to an isostatic pressure of 100–200 MPa transferred through a gaseous medium, usually argon. Employing a combination of plastic deformation, diffusion, and creep, the HIP process results in a compact that is very close to theoretical density. Because of isostatic pressure, the HIP-ed cryomilled material exhibits microstructures with no crystallographic texture [25].

To reduce the cost of the processing and decrease the time spent at high temperature, cold-isostatic pressing (CIPping) has been investigated by many researchers [26]. The extent of consolidation in CIP-ed billets are lower than HIP-ed material, and therefore further deformation processing is required for improved bonding across prior-particles. In one approach, cryomilled and CIP-ed Al 5083 alloy was high strain-rate ($\sim 100/\text{sec}$)

extruded at 500 – 500 C to yield fully consolidated nano-grained extrusions. Grain sizes were less than 50 nm and extremely high strength (> 900 MPa) was obtained [9, 27]. However, this technique cannot be scaled to large dimensions, and moreover ductility was essentially zero.

Vacuum hot-pressing (VHP) is a process where compaction and sintering take place simultaneously and thus the residual porosity is substantially reduced in the bulk material [28-33]. In this research, VHP technique was used to consolidate the cryomilled powders. The cryomilled powder was degassed in Al cans at 300-400 C in vacuum, followed by hot-pressing. The time of degassing ranged from 8-20 hours, and gas analysis was used to ensure the level of degassing prior to VHP. VHP was carried out utilizing standard method.

2.1.5 Secondary Processing Techniques

After the consolidation of the cryomilled powder, the grain size of the compacts are still very low due to the thermal stability arising from oxinitride clusters formed during cryomilling. The compacts have very high strength but suffer from very low ductility due to inadequate bonding across prior particle boundaries (PPB). Therefore, secondary processes such as extrusion, forging and rolling are employed to deform the consolidated billets, whereby shear deformation breaks up oxide/hydroxide layers at the prior particle boundary structure and permit welding of the particles [34]. Deformation processing also introduces mobile dislocations that are beneficial for initiating plastic deformation in the nano crystalline structure.

Extrusion is an effective technique for breaking up prior particle boundaries by imparting plastic shear strain. Suitable combination of die angle, lubrication, and process parameters can be incorporated to ensure reasonable uniformity of microstructure in the extruded billet. Large reduction in area is beneficial to improved ductility, but temperature increase during extrusion can lead to excessive grain growth. Extrusion is a relatively simple approach and in most cases is a one-step process unless multiple passes are desired to achieve large area reduction. Porosity is eliminated to a minimum in billets deformed using the extrusion technique [35].

The extrusion route has been utilized in this project as the secondary processing technique. One casualty of elevated temperature secondary processing is strain energy induced dynamic grain growth [10, 27, 36]. That is why process parameters must be adjusted and optimized to obtain the best combination of strength and ductility.

2.2 Al 5083 Alloys

Al 5083 is a moderate strength light weight aluminum alloy with primarily magnesium and manganese as its constituents. Table 1 shows the nominal composition of Al 5083. The combination of alloying elements provides for good corrosion resistance and results in a formable and weldable alloy. Due to this combination of properties, Al 5083 has

found applications in shipbuilding, rail cars, vehicle bodies, tip truck bodies and pressure vessels. In addition to Mg and Mn, other elements remain from the manufacturing process. Impurities like Fe, Cr, etc. are present in conventional alloys, but are generally not detrimental to ductility at the 300 MPa strength level. At higher strength levels, characteristic of the nanostructured material of current interest, these impurities may play a role in reducing ductility.

Table 1: Nominal composition of AA5083 [6]

Element	Al	Mg	Mn	Cr	Cu	Fe	Si	Ti	Zn	Others
Weight %	92.4 - 95.6	4 - 4.9	0.4 - 1	0.05 - 0.25	≤ 0.1	≤ 0.4	≤ 0.4	≤ 0.15	≤ 0.25	≤ 0.15

CHAPTER 3: RESEARCH APPROACH

The goal of this project was to optimize the strength - ductility combination of a nanostructured near Al-5083 alloy by controlling the microstructure through deformation processing. Figure 5 shows the material processing steps that were followed in this project. The nanostructured powders were obtained by cryomilling a specially prepared gas-atomized batch of near Al-5083 composition using hardened steel balls as milling media. A small amount of stearic acid was used to minimize welding of particles during cryomilling. The cryomilled powders were poured into Al-alloy cans and, following degassing at elevated temperature, they were consolidated by the vacuum hot-pressing (VHP) method. The consolidated material was supplied to New Mexico Tech by DWA Composites, Inc., Chatsworth, CA (we thank Mark Van den Bergh) for conducting the deformation processing investigation for enhancing both ultimate tensile strength and elongation to failure. The microstructure and mechanical properties of the billets were characterized to obtain insight on the structure-property relations in the material.

Figure 5: Material processing steps followed in this project.

The secondary deformation processing method that was used in this project was forward extrusion. In the extrusion process, the VHP consolidated billets were extruded through a die with circular hole. The extrusion ratio, which is the ratio of inlet to outlet area, was maintained at approximately 3:11 in this study. This area ratio corresponds to a true strain of ~ 1.0 , which is actually low compared to commercial extrusion processes. The extrusions were carried out at different temperatures and strain rates to optimize the strength and ductility, to make them suitable for the structural applications. Particular relevance was the fact that strain rate was kept low in order to minimize stress levels, which otherwise could lead to rapid grain growth.

Experimental Procedure and Analysis

3.1 Processing

The vacuum hot-pressed (VHP) billets were used for this study. DWA Aluminum Composites (Chatsworth, CA) carried out the cryomilling of Al 5083 powders followed by the primary consolidation of the powders into the billets. The powder was cryomilled for 24 hours in liquid nitrogen environment. The milled powder was degassed in Al cans at 400 C in vacuum (10^{-5} Torr), followed by vacuum hot-pressing at approximately 300 C. The presence of numerous nitrogen bearing dispersoids contribute to grain size stability even at the high temperature [21]. The as-VHP billet of approximately 75 mm diameter and 60 mm height were cut into sections of approximate size 8.4 X 8.4 sq mm cross section and about 50-60 mm length, see Figure 6.

Figure 6: As-VHP near Al-5083 billet that is sectioned into pieces of approximately 8.4 x 8.4 sq mm cross-section; page normal is the direction of pressing. The right and left outer edges show a distinct marking that corresponds to the Al-alloy can, and which was removed before extrusions.

The billets were then cut to length using a low speed diamond saw cutter according to the die design. Average strain rates during extrusion ranged between 0.05 – 0.25 /sec. For a given strain rate, the ram speed was determined using the formula [37]:

$$\dot{\epsilon} = \frac{6V_o D_o^2 \tan \alpha}{D_o^3 - D_f^3} \cdot \ln R \quad \text{Equation 1}$$

where, V_o is the ram velocity that was controlled by the MTS machine, $\dot{\epsilon}$ is the average true strain rate within the cross section, R is the extrusion ratio, D_o is the billet cross sectional diameter, D_f is the diameter of the extruded product and α is the die angle.

Figure 7a and b show line drawings for the extrusion chamber and die opening, respectively. The die opening angle α was selected as 45 degrees. A thermocouple (K-type thermocouple) was inserted into a hole in the extrusion die in order to obtain the sample temperature, albeit at non-zero distance from the square billet (8.4 x 8.4 mm cross section). The sample along with extrusion chamber was heated inside the clamshell furnace for 120-150 minutes to reach the intended temperature prior to conducting an extrusion run. Temperature of the furnace was controlled precisely within ± 10 C range from the intended temperature. The thermocouple that was inserted into the hole was used to monitor the temperature of the sample to assure that the temperature was representative of the actual billet temperature.

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 7: Small-scale extrusion fixture used for conducting the deformation processing study in this investigation. (a) Line drawing of the main extrusion chamber; (b) line drawing for the extrusion die, (c) Photograph of the extrusion fixture, with the extrusion chamber on the left, the extrusion main opening in the center, and extrusion exit on the right. The small hole in the main chamber on the left shows where a K-type thermocouple was inserted to monitor the temperature of the sample. The material was equilibrated at the extrusion temperature for 15 minutes prior to the extrusion run

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 8: The setup of the apparatus for conducting low strain rate extrusions. (a) Clamshell furnace mounted on a 100 kN MTS load frame for conducting extrusions at elevated temperatures, (b) cutaway view of the partially opened furnace showing the placement of the extrusion fixture, and, (c) close-up of the mounted fixture with the sample inside, showing the punch projecting outside the extrusion chamber. This apparatus can be utilized to conduct extrusions up to 500 C, limited by the temperature capability of the extrusion die material.

Figure 8 shows the extrusion apparatus placed inside a clamshell furnace for conducting extrusion at elevated temperature. The extrusions were conducted on a 100 kN MTS servohydraulic load frame, in order to accurately control the average strain-rate for the extrusion and also to monitor the load during the extrusions. The die outlet had a minimum diameter of 5.5 mm, in order to obtain a true strain around 1, starting from the initial 8.4x8.4 mm cross section billet. The temperature during the extrusion ranged from 250 to 400 C. A lubricant paste with high temperature stability (Permatex® Anti-seize Lubricant, temperature range -52 C to 871 C) was used to minimize the friction between the extruding Al 5083 alloy and the die during the extrusion process. Most of the extruded cylindrical samples of approximately 5.5 mm diameter had a slight curvature and therefore needed some straightening on a press with heated dies. The final billets were cut for different microstructural studies and machined to make dog-bone shaped tensile test samples. These samples were miniature compared to ASTM E9 standard requirements, and therefore the mechanical test results may only be taken as tentative for now.

3.2 Chemical Composition

In a previous study [9] at New Mexico Tech, Al 5083 had been used as the starting material. It was subjected to repeated multi-directional plane strain forging, known as ABC forging in order to enhance mechanical properties. TEM examination of the starting Al-5083 powders showed a microstructure that consisted of fairly large grains, and most importantly the grain boundaries were enriched intermetallic particles of Mg, Fe and Cr. These are illustrated in Figure 9, taken from [38]. TEM sections were sliced from the as-received powders using a focused ion beam (FIB) technique, and were analyzed using energy dispersive spectroscopy (EDS). The distribution and size scale of the particles that decorate the grain boundaries are shown in the two micrographs. The average grain size was approximately 2 μm while the intermetallic particle sizes ranged from 60 to 100 nm. EDS spectra in this figure shows primarily Fe-Al compound with some Mg, although in other regions both Fe and Cr compounds were observed that contained primarily Al and small amounts of Mg and Mn [38].

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 9: (a-b) Microstructure of the base Al 5083 powder that was used in previous investigations (c) energy dispersive spectroscopy (EDS) of the intermetallic particle [9, 38].

Although the particles were crushed into smaller pieces during cryomilling, their presence was observed in the final deformation processed billets. Such brittle intermetallics are detrimental to ductility and therefore in the current project a special batch of near Al-5083 powder was prepared. The rationale was to minimize the intermetallic content and thereby contribute to higher ductility.

Although as-atomized powders were not available, small pieces of the VHP material were sent to Luvak, Inc.® for determining composition using the Direct Current Plasma Emission Spectrometry (DCPES) technique and Inert Gas Fusion technique (for O₂ and N₂). The composition of our material is given in Table 2, where also the standard composition for Al 5083 alloy is given for reference [6].

Table 2: Composition (in weight percent) of 24 hr cryomilled near Al-5083 alloy after vacuum hot-pressing, and comparison with the conventional Al-5083 alloy [6]

Material	Mg	Mn	Cr	Fe*	O	N	Others*	Al
Conventional Al-5083 Alloy	4 - 4.9	0.4-1.0	0.05-0.25	≤0.4	----	----	Please see below	Bal.
Current Near Al-5083 Alloy	3.73	0.47	0.026	0.22	0.48	0.94	-	Bal.

Others* [6]:

Material	Cu	Si	Ti	Zn	Others
Conventional Al-5083 Alloy	0.1	0.4	0.15	0.25	0.15 max.

Table 2 shows that the concentration of Fe is on the low side for this alloy while a substantial decrease in Cr has been possible. Given the precautions taken in fabricating the powder, it is likely that the steel milling media may have contributed to the Fe content. It is notable that the nitrogen content has gone up to almost 1 weight percent, which would contribute to thermal stability and strength. Oxygen is picked up from the atmosphere during the processing prior to consolidation and is responsible for the prior particle boundary network of oxide layers. The PPB oxide layer is responsible for the decreased ductility after the consolidation process and therefore necessitates further processing by deformation. The hydrogen content in the hot pressed billet was not measured. In this regard, hydrogen can be picked up from the stearic acid (used as PCA) during cryomilling and it is harmful to ductility of Al alloys.

3.3 Mechanical Tests

Room temperature compression and tensile tests were performed at a strain rate of 0.0005 /sec using an MTS universal testing system with 25 kN load capability. Tests were conducted on both as the as-VHP and extruded samples. The extruded cylindrical samples were machined to make dog bone type tensile specimens with 13 mm gauge length and 2 or 2.5 mm gauge diameter. In order to reduce residual stresses arising from processing and subsequent machining, the samples were heat treated prior to RT testing. The tensile grips were of a slotted button-hole type, such that the samples were held at the outer periphery of the fillet radius. The flattening of the curved extruded billets created flats on the sample, and threading would have reduced the cross section at the grips and led to failure at the threads and not in the sample gage length.

Figure 10 shows a tensile sample gripped by the conical shaped bright button-head type fixtures that were screwed to the black cylindrical rods constituting the load train. The load cell is not visible but lies at the bottom side of the photograph, while the hydraulically controlled actuator is at the top. The small gage length prevented direct contact between the extensometer and the sample. Therefore, displacement measurements were made between the two cylindrical rods in the load-train using the Al-alloy fixtures, culminating in the extensometer. This arrangement naturally led to displacements that were larger than the sample. The apparent displacements were assumed to be linearly proportional to the load, although in reality some non-linear displacements likely occurred where the button-head type grips dug into the fillet section of the test sample as well as at the thread that connected these grips to the load train. In a later section we show how we corrected for the added compliance and thereby obtained a better estimate of the elongation to failure of the samples.

Figure 10: A tensile sample mounted on MTS load frame.

Figure 11 shows the tensile test specimen before and after failure. The method of gripping did contribute to stress concentration at the start of the uniform cross section of the samples, but most of the samples exhibited failure outside the fillet area.

Figure 11: Tensile test sample (before and after testing)

3.4 Microstructural Analysis Techniques

The analysis techniques employed to investigate the microstructure of the NC Al 5083 alloy after processing were Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM), Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM), X-ray Diffractometry (XRD), and the EBSD technique. In particular, X-ray diffraction technique was used to estimate the nanograin size. The TEM technique remains a very effective technique in determining grain sizes and morphology of nanostructured materials. However, sample preparation can be challenging and microstructure analysis is limited to very small sizes (of the order of a micron square area) at a time. TEM results were obtained from our collaborators [39] and are provided for purpose of cross-correlation. Grain sizes obtained from TEM measurements were usually based on an average of 150 grains and calculated using the line intercept method. EBSD images of the extruded sample was obtained from [40], and provided insight on the multiple grain sizes present in the microstructure.

3.5 X-Ray Diffraction Analysis for Grain Size Measurements

XRD is a useful tool that is commonly used for grain size measurement in nanocrystalline materials. Through measurement of the diffraction peak width, the average grain size may be estimated using the Scherrer formula [41]:

$$D = \frac{K \lambda}{\beta_D \cos \theta} \quad \text{Equation 2}$$

where D is the average grain diameter of the material (\AA), λ is the wavelength of the X-ray radiation used (\AA), β_D is the true broadening (radians), θ is the Bragg angle (degrees) and K is the shape factor (approximately 0.9). One problem with this approach is that broadening does not result from grain size alone but other sources may be responsible for peak broadening. These different sources include instrumental factors and the presence of defects in the perfect lattice, the latter giving rise to microstrains in different grains of a polycrystalline solid. These can be accounted for in arriving at a grain size using peak profile analysis. Warren and Jones proposed methods for correcting instrumental broadening based on a Fourier transform analysis of the measured x-ray profile, and experimental analysis details are given by Klug and Alexander [42].

Established methods account for the influence of strain on peak broadening. One such method requires that an XRD profile of a standard sample be used in the analysis [43, 44]. The standard sample must be free of strain and can be an annealed sample of the same material. The important parameters are defined as follows: β_h is the integral breadth of the measured diffraction peaks for the material of interest, β_f is the integral breadth of the diffraction peaks for the standard sample.

As mentioned earlier, the measured profile is a convolution of the instrumental broadening (the broadening from the instrument itself) profile and the intrinsic

broadening (stemming from small grain size and microstrain) profile. Subtraction of the influence of the instrumental broadening can be made on the basis of an assumption regarding the shapes of the intrinsic profile and instrumental profile [45-47]. The two most commonly assumed line shapes of XRD profiles are the Gaussian [46, 48],

$$I(x) = I_o \exp \left[-\pi \frac{(2\theta - 2\theta_B)^2}{\beta_G^2} \right] = I_o \exp \left[-\ln 2 \times \frac{(2\theta - 2\theta_B)^2}{hwhm^2} \right] \quad \text{Equation 3}$$

and the Cauchy [46, 48],

$$I(x) = \frac{I_o}{1 + \left\{ \left(\frac{\pi}{\beta_L} \right)^2 (2\theta - 2\theta_B)^2 \right\}} = \frac{I_o}{1 + \left\{ \left(\frac{2\theta - 2\theta_B}{hwhm} \right)^2 \right\}} \quad \text{Equation 4}$$

If the intrinsic and instrumental profiles (the latter is represented by the measured profile of the annealed sample) are assumed to be Cauchy-Cauchy (CC), Gaussian-Gaussian (GG) or Cauchy-Gaussian (CG), respectively, the following equations are obtained [43, 48].

$$\beta_g = \beta_h - \beta_f \quad \text{Equation 5}$$

$$\beta_g = (\beta_h^2 - \beta_f^2)^{1/2} \quad \text{Equation 6}$$

$$\beta_g = \beta_h - \frac{\beta_f^2}{\beta_h} \quad \text{Equation 7}$$

where β_g is the intrinsic broadening due to the combined effects of small grain size and microstrain.

There are variations in final grain size depending on the equations used. In this study, the Cauchy-Cauchy (CC) equation (5) was used.

The grain size broadening in the material can be expressed by the Scherrer formula as [44],

$$\beta_D = K\lambda / D \cos\theta \quad \text{Equation 8}$$

The microstrain broadening can be written as [44],

$$\beta_s = 4e \tan\theta \quad \text{Equation 9}$$

where, e is an approximate upper limit of the internal microstrain or lattice distortion caused by dislocations, faults, etc. Assuming the grain size broadening profile and the microstrain broadening profile to be Cauchy-Cauchy (CC), the total line broadening, sum of these two broadening (after subtracting the effect of instrument broadening) is expressed as:

$$\beta_g = \beta_D + \beta_s \quad \text{Equation 10}$$

Substituting Equations 8 and 9 into Equation 10, the following equation results, which is essentially the Williamson-Hall modification to the Scherrer equation to account for both crystallite size and microstrain broadening:

$$\beta_g \cos \theta = 4e \sin \theta + k\lambda/D \quad \text{Equation 11}$$

When $\beta_g \cos \theta$ is plotted against $\sin \theta$ for XRD reflections, the data should be on a straight line, with a slope of $4e$ and an intercept of $k\lambda/D$. The latter is then used to back out the average grain size, D . This approach shows that broadening due to grain size can be differentiated from broadening due to internal microstrain.

In this project, X-ray profiles were acquired using the PANalytical XPert Pro diffractometer with Cu K α radiation source ($\lambda = 0.15406$ nm), with 2θ ranging from 30–120° at a scan rate of 0.02°/s. In the case for the current study, strain free silicon powder with large grains was used as the standard. The K α 2 peaks were subtracted using the HighScore Plus Software. Analyses were carried out by taking consideration of 5 peaks. XRD profiles cannot be satisfactorily represented with either Gaussian or Cauchy functions in most cases. When profiles arise from the size effect, they are approximately represented with Cauchy function [46]. Thus, peaks were best fitted with the Lorentzian/Cauchy function. Fityk software was used to fit the peaks of the XRD profiles. Fityk shows half width at half maximum (HWHM) values of the fitted profile. Thus, the following relationship was used to calculate integral breadths of Lorentzian/Cauchy profile from FWHM (or, 2 X HWHM) of same Lorentzian/Cauchy profile:

$$\beta_L = \left(\frac{\pi}{2}\right) \times FWHM_L \quad \text{Equation 12}$$

The net sample broadening due to microstrain and grain size was obtained by subtracting the integral breadth from the standard Si sample with large grains from the integral breadth of the measured diffraction profile of sample, using equation 5.

CHAPTER 4: RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Tensile Tests

Tensile test samples were heat treated after machining. Tensile tests were conducted at room temperature at a strain rate of 0.0005 s^{-1} . Due to the restriction from sample size, the extensometer was not attached directly to the sample; rather a special setup was developed in which the extensometer was attached to the grips to record the crosshead position, see Figure 10. This naturally made the system more compliant, which was significant in the term of lowered elastic modulus. Since the change in distance between the cylindrical fixtures (Figure 10), ΔX , was measured, the strain value calculated is called apparent strain. ΔX can be expressed as:

$$\Delta X = \Delta S + \Delta L_0 \quad \text{Equation 13}$$

Where ΔL_0 is the change in actual gage length of the sample, and ΔS is the total machine deformation which here includes elastic and inelastic deformation of the sample fillet region that is loaded by the conical button-head grips and the loading of the threads of the conical fixture which was connected to the black cylindrical fixture (Figure 10). We assume that the deformation of this load train is elastic, although in reality there is some inelastic deformation where the grip bites into the specimen. The overall deformation of the load train, ΔS , is thus:

$$\Delta X = s \cdot P + \Delta L_0 \quad \text{Equation 14}$$

where s is defined as the compliance of the load train. Thus, the apparent strain can be expressed in terms of the real strain of the specimen $\epsilon_{\text{specimen}}$ as:

$$\epsilon_{\text{apparent}} = \left(\frac{s \cdot A}{L_0} \right) \cdot \sigma + \epsilon_{\text{specimen}} \quad \text{Equation 15}$$

Where A is the area of the sample and L_0 is the gage length (12 mm). To utilize the method described above in finding the corrected strains for the samples, the following steps were followed. At first the true stress is plotted against the true strains from the tensile test. A trend line is drawn for the linear portion and the slope is used to calculate the compliance. To do this, the Hooke's Law is used and the above equation gives:

$$s = \left(\frac{E_{\text{specimen}}}{E_{\text{apparent}}} - 1 \right) \cdot \frac{L_0}{A E_{\text{specimen}}} \quad \text{Equation 16}$$

Here we know the actual modulus of the Al 5083 to be around 70 GPa, but as the sample size is very small, to get a harmonious data from the samples, 40 GPa was used to

calculate system compliance instead of 70 GPa. The apparent modulus is the slope of the trend line as discussed above. Then the true strains were corrected using the equation. The apparent modulus varied in each test and thus the compliance was calculated for each of the samples to get the corrected strains. Figure 12 illustrates the stress strain curves with and without strain correction, and it can be seen that the corrected strain leads to a failure strain which is less than the apparent strain. In all samples the strain correction procedure was incorporated for plotting the data.

Figure 12: Stress-strain curves for a sample extruded at 350 C and subsequently annealed at 400 C for 2 hours. The curve with lower initial slope is a plot of the true stress versus strain from the raw data, while the curve with higher slope is based on strains that were corrected for specimen compliance effect.

Figure 13: RT tensile test results showing true stress versus true strain plot of samples extruded at different temperatures at the same 0.05 /s average extrusion strain rate. All samples were annealed at 400 C for 2 hours following machining.

Figure 14: Stress-strain plots of samples extruded under identical conditions but annealed at different temperatures for 2 hours.

Figure 13 shows true stress-strain curves for samples extruded at average strain rate of 0.05/sec but at different temperatures. Extrusions at 350 and 400 C indicate reasonably good strength-ductility combination with true tensile strength in the range 730 – 760 MPa and elongation to failure of approximately 3%. Conversely, the extrusion at 450 C shows poor strength and the extrusion at 300 C exhibits poor ductility. The samples with strength above 700 MPa exhibit a stress drop after reaching the peak value, indicating possible softening of the material. This softening can be explained by the fact that a high density of dislocations is created at the interior of grains during the extrusion process [49]. During tensile loading, the high density of dislocations can induce dynamic recovery and thus the material exhibits work softening immediately after yielding, leading to plastic instability and the onset of necking. The density of dislocations depends on total true strain and temperature during extrusion. A comparison of tensile curves of two samples in Figure 13, both extruded at 400 C, but one sample with total true strain of 1 (sample T071113_C) and another sample (marked AB forged and extruded) with total true strain of 1.6, that the latter sample shows earlier work softening and lower strain to failure. A higher dislocation density could accumulate with higher extrusion strains, and so the observed earlier softening of the AB sample would tend to back up the argument that softening is a result of high dislocation density accumulated in nano grained microstructures that have undergone various processing steps. In case of the sample extruded at 450 C, the density of dislocations likely remained low because of recovery of dislocations during extrusion itself. Thus, this sample probably had grains which were low of dislocations after extrusion, resulting in some work hardening during tensile

loading and an increase in strain to failure. The strength probably dropped as a result of larger grains with low density of dislocations.

Another contributing factor to softening is that nano-grains do not allow for dislocation entrapment or interaction inside the grains; in other words, work hardening is difficult. As dislocations became more mobile with accumulated strain, the stress to move them may diminish, thereby contributing to softening. The small diameter of the samples may also have contributed to the softening curve. Generally larger test samples are used to permit deformation at the bulk scale. Smaller test samples have limited number of grains and are more susceptible to tensile instability. Thus, small samples often tend to exhibit decreased statistical reliability. However, multiple tests of material extruded at 400 C and extruded at 0.05/sec showed extremely reproducible results. While these results may have been handicapped by small sample size, nevertheless they confirm that the extrusion process and test conditions are robust and can be extended to larger billets.

Figure 14 shows the effect of different annealing conditions on the tensile properties. The plot shows minimal effect of annealing temperature on the tensile strength. This is a useful result since samples can therefore be annealed up to the high temperatures in order to reduce residual stresses to a minimum. Indeed, 400 C was used as the standard annealing temperature for most of the extrusions.

4.2 Fracture Surface

After carrying out the tensile tests, the fracture surfaces of the samples were observed using SEM.

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

Figure 15: Fracture surface of a sample (T071113_C) extruded at 400 C at 0.05 /sec strain rate and heat treated at 400 C for 2 hours, at different magnifications.

Figure 15 shows micrographs of a sample extruded at 400 C at an average strain rate of 0.05/sec. The micrographs are taken from the same region of the sample with increasing magnifications to better understand different features of the fracture surface. Figure (a) shows that there are lots of voids, which are very large and deep in size. But no apparent dimples and tearing ridges are observed on the fracture surface at this magnification level. Thus it became necessary to magnify the region to observe the dimples on the fracture surface. Regions of figure (a) are shown with higher magnifications in figure (b), (c), and (d). It is obvious from figure (d) that many dimples are as small as 300 - 400 nm. Although the ridges of these dimples are not very sharp, they are indeed distinguishable as ridges, suggesting that the sample failed in a ductile mode. The deep protrusions in figure (a) likely indicate that they originate at nanograin locations. These locations are not planar and therefore show large pullouts in the form of protrusions. Each of these protrusions has lots of non-planar surfaces as can be seen from (b) and (c), and when these non-planar surfaces are observed at higher magnifications as in (d), it is only then that we observe nano-level dimples. As a concluding remark, we can say that the extruded sample fractured with deep protrusions which do not give a sense of ductile failure, but the nano-level shallow dimples constituting the non-planar surfaces of these protrusions indicate ductile-like failure.

4.3 Microstructural Analysis

The nano grain sizes of the as-VHP and extruded material were estimated using the XRD technique and utilizing the Williamson-Hall method. It is important to note here that this peak-broadening based approach is only valid for crystallite sizes up to about 100 nm [50] beyond which the peak width becomes so narrow that crystallite size cannot be determined with any degree of certainty. Indeed, TEM and EBSD analyses that are discussed later indicate that the extruded material had grain sizes at three different length scales, the largest ones at the 2 – 5 μm level. Consequently, the discussion in this section only applies to grains at the lowest length scale. Additionally, TEM results do confirm the validity of grain sizes determined here using the simpler XRD technique.

Following collection of the raw $K\alpha$ XRD data, the $K\alpha_2$ peaks were stripped using the HighScore Plus[®] software. Then the background was subtracted using the Fityk software [51]. The peaks were best fitted in Fityk software using the Lorentzian function. In Fityk software, the Levenberg-Marquardt (LM) algorithm was chosen as the non-linear least square curve fitting method. Then the half width at half maximum intensity (HWHM) in degree unit was obtained using the software. The HWHM intensities were multiplied by 2 and converted into radian unit to obtain the corresponding full width at half maximum intensity (FWHM). The corresponding integral breadths were obtained using equation 12. To separate out the intrinsic broadening from the instrumental broadening, a standard material of coarse grained Si powder was utilized using identical diffractometer settings [46]. Ten peaks were used for the coarse grained Si, and the integral breadths (β_f) are tabulated in Table 3.

Table 3: Integral breadths for the coarse grained Si standard

HWHM (degree)	2θ (degree)	2θ (radian)	FWHM (radian)	Integral Breadth, β_f (radian)
0.026443	30.08203	0.52503047	0.000923034	0.001449898
0.049769	47.29744	0.82549606	0.001737259	0.002728879
0.06093	56.11444	0.97938174	0.002126866	0.003340873
0.071129	69.12157	1.20639898	0.002482871	0.003900084
0.075379	76.36686	1.33285315	0.002631214	0.004133101
0.070164	88.02054	1.53624823	0.002449168	0.003847144
0.087809	94.94264	1.65706167	0.003065103	0.004814653
0.107046	106.6979	1.86222966	0.00373661	0.005869454
0.111499	114.0832	1.99112746	0.003892056	0.006113628
0.161501	127.537	2.22594057	0.005637441	0.008855272

The β_f values were plotted against the 2θ (radian) values as shown in Figure 16 below:

Figure 16: β_f Vs 2θ (radian) for the Si powder standard

The data were best fitted by a second order polynomial curve. This curve was utilized to find the instrumental broadening (integral breadths) by interpolation at each peak position of the x-ray profiles of our near-Al 5083 using the equation:

$$y = M_0 + M_1 \cdot x + M_2 \cdot x^2 \quad \text{Equation 17}$$

where y is the interpolated instrumental broadening (interpolated β_f) for a nanograined extruded sample, M_0 , M_1 and M_2 are constants shown in Figure 16, and x is the peak position 2θ (radian) for any of the nanograined samples of interest. Now, for a given sample, the β_h values which have contributions from both instrumental broadening and intrinsic broadening were obtained by fitting the XRD profile with Lorentzian function utilizing the Fityk software. Then the broadening of peaks due to the grain size and the microstrain, designated as β_g was calculated using the Cauchy-Cauchy (CC) equation 5, as stated earlier. In this way, Table 4 was produced for sample T093013B that was extruded at 350 C at a strain rate of 0.05 /sec and annealed at 400 C for 2 hours.

Table 4: Table for Williamson-Hall plot for sample T093013B extruded at 350 C at a strain rate of 0.05 /sec and annealed at 400 C for 2 hours

Interpolated β_r (radian)	FWHM (radian)	β_h (radian)	β_g (radian)	2Θ (°)	2Θ (radian)	Θ (radian)	$B_g \cos\Theta$ (radian)	$\sin\Theta$
0.0022028	0.00242	0.0038	0.00159	38.5554	0.67291885	0.33646	0.00151	0.33015
0.0023785	0.00193	0.00304	0.00066	44.7822	0.78159701	0.3908	0.00061	0.38093
0.0031992	0.00249	0.00391	0.00071	65.1017	1.13623849	0.56812	0.0006	0.53805
0.0039281	0.00278	0.00437	0.00045	78.184	1.3645677	0.68228	0.00035	0.63057
0.0041946	0.003	0.00471	0.00052	82.3707	1.43764045	0.71882	0.00039	0.6585

$\beta_g \cos \Theta$ values were then plotted versus the $\sin \Theta$ values in Figure 17, giving rise to the Williamson-Hall plot.

Figure 17: Williamson-Hall plot for sample T093013B extruded at 350 C at a strain rate of 0.05 /sec and annealed at 400 C for 2 hours

From Figure 17, the slope and y-intercept of the best fitted straight line were calculated to be - 0.0026087 and 0.0020135 respectively. The grain size was finally calculated using the Scherer equation shown below:

$$\text{Average grain size, nm} = K\lambda/Y\text{-intercept} \quad \text{Equation 18}$$

where K is the shape factor (0.94), λ is the wavelength of Cu K α radiation (0.1540598 nm) and Y-intercept calculated above is 0.0020135.

In this way the grain size of this extruded sample was determined to be 70 nm. The same approach was used for all other samples.

The quality of fit was not particularly good in Figure 17. If we assume that the scatter in the intercept is of the order of standard deviation of data from the intercept of best fit straight line (approximately 0.002 in Figure 17), the grain size would be between 60 nm to 90 nm. Nevertheless, there was reasonable consistency in the way that the nano grain sizes changed with processing condition, and therefore provides a reasonable level of confidence in the calculated grain sizes.

Table 5: XRD grain size data

Sample number	Total true strain	Extrusion temperature (C)	Average extrusion strain rate (/sec)	Annealing temperature (C)	Heat treatment duration (hr)	True tensile strength (MPa)	Total Elongation to failure (%)	Grain size from XRD (nm)
T071113_C	1	400	0.05	400	2 h	740	3.7	90
T093013B	1	350	0.05	400	2	770	4.2	70
T100213	1.6	400	0.05	400	2	708	2.9	80
As-received VHP	-	-	-	-	-	650	-	36
T093013A	1	400	0.05	200	2	700	3.75	-

The grain size data for different samples are shown graphically in Figure 18.

Figure 18: Grain size data for different samples (extrusion temperature and total true strain are given inside parentheses, all extruded at 0.05 /sec rate)

Figure 18 shows that the grain size of the as-VHP sample was 35 nm whereas the extruded samples showed higher grain sizes with increasing extrusion temperature. The nanograins grew in size as a result of high temperature during extrusion processing.

In order to shed additional insight on grain size data, the samples were analyzed at the University of Central Florida using a high resolution TEM.

Figure 19: TEM bright field micrographs of the as-received VHP material illustrating a multi-scale microstructure. (a) A single grain occupies region 1, while region 2 is composed of grains sizes in the range 0.2 to 0.3 μm as separately determined by HCDF. (b) a different region of the same sample showing an elongated coarse grain instead of an equiaxed one. (c-d) Bright and HCDF images of a region similar to location 3 of part (a) showing nano grains less than 80 nm.

Figure 19 shows TEM micrographs of the as-received VHP material. It illustrates a multi-scale microstructure consisting of primarily 3 grain sizes. The large grains were in the 0.5

– 2 μm range and they were relatively free of dislocations. The second level of grain sizes consisted of submicron or ultrafine grains of 0.15 - 0.25 μm size, these being deduced from region 2 in Figure 19(a) using hollow-cone dark-field (HCDF) imaging. Their volume fraction was relatively low. Finally, the bright and dark field images of Figure 19(c-d) show areas, such as region 3 of the figure (a), where only nano grains are present with sizes in the 20-60 nm range. Our X-ray based result indicated an average grain size of 35 nm, which is consistent with the nano grain sizes determined using TEM. Also, as indicated earlier, X-ray analysis is inadequate for crystallite sizes above 100 nm because peak width becomes very narrow.

The multiple grain sizes were unanticipated when the X-ray investigation was conducted, and serves to point out the need to evaluate microstructures utilizing multiple techniques. The largest grain sizes were still sufficiently small so that etching could not bring out their presence during our microstructural study at NMT. The question still remains as to what was the volume fraction of the nanograins in the as-VHP microstructure. Unfortunately, we are unable to answer this question at the present time since multiple TEM micrographs from different regions of the sample are necessary to obtain reasonable statistics. Our initial estimate based on a few TEM micrographs is that it was limited to about 60%, but EBSD analysis over a larger area is needed to confirm this value. In this context please note that in the past [9] grain sizes greater than 300 nm could be brought out fairly easily in EBSD scans of cryomilled Al-5083 following thermomechanical processing using the ABC forging technique.

Figure 20: EBSD image of cryomilled Al-5083 following thermomechanical processing using the ABC forging technique [9].

A possible reason for the multiscale microstructure is some deficiency in the 24 hour cryomilling. Atomized powders of the 'cleaner' near Al-5083 alloy composition are likely to be softer than commercial powders because of the lower alloy content and

minimization of intermetallics, and may have contributed to particle bonding/welding on ball impact. As a result, regions of the larger bonded particles may have been shielded from the impact deformation and simply recovered during subsequent vacuum hot pressing. The TEM results suggested that large grains were often fairly free of dislocations, however, other regions contained high dislocation density. Overall, the combination of X-ray analysis and TEM shows that 24-hour cryomilling of this near Al-5083 material was insufficient for conversion to a full nanograined structure. Longer cryomilling time may be necessary for full conversion, although the presence of the multiscale microstructure in the as-VHP condition may also be a benefit to improved ductility and toughness in the thermomechanically processed condition. This is because lack of dislocation multiplication and associated work hardening is a disadvantage of nanostructured alloys and so the presence of larger grains can contribute to ductility by increasing the work hardening rate and also serving to blunt premature cracks.

Figure 21: (a, b) TEM micrographs of sample T071113_C extruded at 400 C at 0.05 /sec strain rate and heat treated at 400 C for 2 hours. [39]

Figure 21 shows the TEM microstructure of a sample that was extruded at 400 C at 0.05/sec strain rate and heat treated at 400 C for 2 hours. It shows that there are larger elongated grains which are likely the result of extrusion of the larger grains observed in the as-VHP sample. The aspect ratio was around 2-3, which would necessarily imply the presence of strong texture in the large grain regions. Although TEM was insufficient to give estimates of average grain size in the extruded condition, EBSD analysis shown later suggest that the length of these larger grains was in the range of 3 – 7 μm while their widths were about 1-2 μm . The nano grains now ranged between 60 – 130 nm. This size range is once again consistent with that from the X-ray grain size determination.

Figure 22 shows EBSD images of the sample extruded at 400 C at 0.05/sec strain rate. The micrographs cover a much larger area than possible in the TEM, and therefore provide improved information of the size of the larger and mid-size grains in the extruded condition. The blue color represents a (111) pole in the extrusion direction, and so the

coarse grains of 3-7 μm length and 2-4 μm wide cross section do indicate strong (111) fiber texture. The sizes of grains are better highlighted in Figure 23, which is a band contrast image that approximately fills in the pixels at boundaries of grains that are difficult to fully evaluate in terms of orientation in the EBSD images of Figure 22. As may be observed, Figure 22 is heavily pixilated compared to Figure 23.

The intermediate size grains have lengths of 1-3 μm and widths of about 0.5 μm , but now the orientations are more random. The very dark areas in Figures 22 and 23 are not holes in the sample based on optical and SEM observation. Rather, we believe that they represent nano grains of 60 – 130 nm size that were captured by both X-ray and TEM techniques. Overall, the combination of the three techniques is finally capable of bringing out the proper microstructure of this material in a satisfactory manner.

We would like to make a final remark with regard to the X-ray analysis. The strong (111) texture in the coarse grains will contribute to enhanced intensity in the (111) peak in the diffraction pattern, since the X-ray data were obtained from the extrusion cross-sections. This effect may have influenced the peak width at half maximum for this pole and a possible factor contributing to the observed deviation from the best fit curve for the first point of the Williamson-Hall plot of Figure 17. Incidentally, the second point from the left in Figure 17 corresponds to the (100) diffraction, although in this case the influence of texture is not all that clear at the moment.

Figure 22: EBSD images of the extruded 400C/0.05/sec sample showing, (a) longitudinal section, and, (b) transverse cross-section. The marker length is 5 μm in both the micrographs. The inverse pole figure (IPF) colors - red, green and blue represent (100), (110) and (111) poles along the extrusion direction, respectively. [40]

(a)

(b)

Figure 23: Band contrast images of the same regions in Figure 22, showing more details of the EBSD. [40]

CHAPTER 5: CONCLUSIONS

The objective of this research was to develop a secondary processing route to obtain nano-grained material of high stability with optimized strength/ductility combination. An extrusion technique was used to process vacuum hot-pressed billet of cryomilled “clean” Al-Mg alloy, close to the Al 5083 specification. The rationale was that the cryomilling, VHP and extrusion techniques were all amenable to scale up, thereby circumventing limitations of severe plastic deformation techniques in fabricating strong nanostructured alloys. Results obtained in this research are summarized as follows:

- The 24 hour cryomilled near Al-5083 'clean' alloy that was extruded at 350-400 C at a low strain rate of 0.05 /sec and further annealed at 400 C/2hrs, showed a good strength/ductility combination, namely, 740-760 MPa true tensile strength and total elongation to failure of 3.7-4.2 % in tension at RT.
- XRD results, where peak widths were analyzed using a combination of Williamson-Hall plot and Scherer equation, indicated an increase in nano-grain size with increasing extrusion temperature. Thus, the average nanograin size increased from 35 nm in the as-VHP to 90 nm in the 400 C extruded plus annealed condition. The size increase is relatively small for this grain size range.
- TEM observations conducted at UCF confirmed the XRD results at the finest nano-grain size; specifically 20 - 60 nm to 60 – 130 nm for the as-VHP and extruded conditions, respectively. However, TEM micrographs indicated grain sizes at three different length scales for even the as-VHP condition, being 0.5 – 2 μm for the largest grains. These results suggest inadequate 24 hour cryomilling of the near Al-5083 alloy, however the in situ formed multiscale microstructure may be favorable for good strength-ductility combination.
- EBSD were utilized to obtain grain structure information over a larger area of the extruded material compared to TEM samples. It failed to resolve grain size below 100 nm, but provided useful data for the larger grain sizes. The largest grains were elongated with an aspect ratio of about 3 and grain lengths in the 3 – 7 μm range and overwhelmingly had (111) preferred orientation in the extrusion direction. Although this texture is often observed in extruded ingot metallurgy Al-alloys, the texture was stronger in our case and likely from constraint from surrounding stronger nano and mid-size grains. The midsize grains were in the 0.5 – 2 μm range and may be from grain growth of both the nano and mid-size grains in the as-VHP material.
- Thus, the results indicate a need to analyze microstructures of nano grained P/M alloys at multiple length scales.
- Fracture surfaces exhibited ductile-dimple failure although often the nano-level dimples were extremely shallow. These extremely shallow dimples may be associated with nano grains which may have failed as ductile failure.

CHAPTER 6: FUTURE WORK

Possible future work is listed below:

1. Larger extrusions of the same material need to be fabricated to make mechanical test specimens that meet ASTM size requirements. Larger volume samples would provide statistically more significant results and validate results from the current investigation.
2. The results quoted in the thesis overwhelmingly refer to samples extruded at 1.0 true strain. Extrusions should be conducted with larger extrusion ratio to evaluate how it may influence strength-ductility combination.
3. Given the multiscale microstructure of the as-VHP material, it would be useful to cryomill the 'clean' alloy for longer time period to evaluate how it may influence structure-property relations.

EBSD examinations should be conducted from the very beginning of characterization, to evaluate the type of microstructures that are anticipated during thermomechanical processing.

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